

WEB BASED PHARMACY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

Sanilka Jayarathna¹, Ruwani Senarathne², Malkanthi Samarasinghe³,
Kavinga Elamulla⁴

*Department of Information Technology, Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce,
University of Sri Jayewardenepura*

*¹sanilkajayarathna97@gmail.com, ²ruwani.rasangi@gmail.com,
³malkanthi@sjp.ac.lk, ⁴kavinga.elamulla@sjp.ac.lk*

Background

Overview of the Business Domain

Our selected organization is a pharmacy which is situated in Digana. Thilina Perera is the owner of the pharmacy, and there are few employees in this pharmacy. Usually, eight suppliers provide medicines to the pharmacy, and customers purchase medicines by presenting them to the pharmacy physically.

Current Situation of the Existing System

In the existing system, several processes such as purchasing medicines from suppliers, selling medicines for customers, and maintaining inventories are done by the pharmacists of the pharmacy.

The pharmacy maintains books and journals to keep all inventory records and supplier information related to their business activities. Also, they do not maintain any records related to customers' information.

However, with the Covid 19 pandemic, the pharmacy started to supply medicines to customers over telephone calls and through social media like WhatsApp, Viber etc.

System Analysis

Problem Analysis

- This organization uses a manual system to track all day-to-day business activities like inventory records, sales records, and suppliers' information in the organization. All these records are maintained in traditional books and journals.

- Also, this organization doesn't have a proper system to get online orders from their customers during this covid 19 period. They are getting orders only through telephone calls and it doesn't work efficiently as expected.
- This organization doesn't have a system to keep online order records and offline sales records in the organization resulting that these records are not updated with their physical inventory level day by day.

Requirement Analysis

The following details show the functional requirements along with the main modules.

1. User Management Module – This module maintains all users of the system. Following are the main functions,
 - Login, logout, sign up, change password and view profiles related to customers
 - Create, update, search, and delete pharmacist's accounts
 - Add another admin and change owner (admin) account
2. Inventory & Supplier Management Module – This module manages the inventory of the pharmacy with the following main functions,
 - Add product categories and stocks with expiry dates
 - Search products for availability of the inventory
 - Update the inventory from the online and offline orders
3. Order Management Module – This module is responsible for handling the online orders. Following are the main functions,
 - Place and track the online orders
 - Send and receive dispatch and order receiving notes
 - View, receive, update online and offline orders, confirm or cancel the orders via automatic emails
4. Billing & Sales Management Module – This module is responsible for monetary. Following are the main functions,
 - Create bills, maintain monetary accounts and sales info

System Development

The high-level solution architecture diagram of the implemented pharmacy management system is shown below.

Figure 1: High-level architecture

Development Methodology used:

Laravel framework is used to develop the web application with Bootstrap. Also, MySQL is used as the database. XAMPP is used as the database management server environment for developments.

Technologies used:

Software requirements - Laravel, HTML, CSS, JavaScript, Bootstrap, MySQL, Apache

Hardware requirements - Hosting Server, RAM 1GB or more, Hard Disk Space 5GB or more, Processor Speed 1GHz or more

Conclusion

Online orders are managed through this system. Also, the owner and pharmacist can use it to handle all inventory records and sales records. In the future, the mobile app will be introduced, a payment gateway and supplier management component will be integrated into the system.

References

<https://www.w3schools.com/>,1998

https://www.tutorialspoint.com/web_development_tutorials.htm